

Current Balance	178,771	How do you see the expansion of your business?
Current Savings	24,425	What type of products do you offer?
Current Investments	244,121	How do you see the future of your industry?
Current Loans	75,382	What are your main competitors?
Current Assets	844,179	How do you see the future of your company?
Current Liabilities	177,145	What are your main challenges?
Current Equity	667,034	What are your main opportunities?
Current Debt	447,771	What are your main risks?
Current Income	10,700	What are your main strengths?
Current Expenses	178,000	What are your main weaknesses?
Current Profit	4,567,284	What are your main goals?

Market Strategy

Marketing strategy is a plan to increase sales and achieve advantages over other competitors. It includes short-term and long-term activities of marketing that has to do with the use of advertising, public relations, and other promotional techniques. The objectives will be based on your goals and the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good idea of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you what you are going to work with your targets etc.

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Putting your strategy into action is how your marketing plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you what you are going to work with your targets etc. It may be through networking, advertising etc. Having the perfect timing with your activities to fit your customers buying cycles will help you saving money and maximizing sales. The marketing plan should be innovative. It should have the details on how your sales are followed up and the activities you doing to develop your offers.

It is a process to allow an organization to focus resources on the greatest opportunities to increase sales and achieve the company's target. Marketing strategy's goal is to increase sales and achieve advantage over other competitors.

THE DAILY

FAKE NEWS

ECONOMY OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

WORLD BANK'S STOCK AT ALL-TIME HIGH / US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOW

US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOW

It is a process to allow an organization to focus resources on the greatest opportunities to increase sales and achieve the company's target. Marketing strategy's goal is to increase sales and achieve advantage over other competitors. It includes short-term and long-term activities of marketing that has to do with the analysis of a company's situation and contribute to its objectives. The objectives will be based on how you gain sales by acquiring and keeping customers.

A marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good outcome of your sales and marketing activities.

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Content optimization in political communication:

lessons from the fake news production sites in Veles, Macedonia

Raluca Petre, Sara Trajckhevska³⁷

Abstract

In this paper we explore internet marketing and fake news production as new media content regimes based on audience profiling.

We undertook a field study of the content enterprises from Veles Macedonia and understood the organic mechanics of fake news production.

The deep-seated problem that we identified was the instrumentalisation of content for political and material ends. Basically, the content producers give the audiences exactly what they want to hear, irrespective of truth. This kind of content enterprise is not likely to disappear, but to thrive, because it is lucrative. The commodity value of fake news is higher than the public service value of journalistic content. These optimization tactics are widely used on the Internet; we believe that the recent success of the populist AUR Party in Romania is a recent illustration of the same practice.

Keywords: Content optimization, Fake news, Internet marketing, Audience profiling, Veles Macedonia

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1. The context

Democratic society is a polity where citizens freely choose their representatives, and delegate to them the power as well as the responsibility of decision on public matters. At the same time, the situation that we are discussing in this paper is a strange one whereby non-citizens have got the power to influence voting decisions over a polity that is not their own.

It is as if in ancient Athens barbarian non-citizens would have a say over the decisions of the rightful Athenians. Imagine that all of a sudden, some foreigners would have the outfit, the skills, and the means to get to the agora and display rhetorical skills and sophisticated argumentation, to the delight of an excited crowd of voters.

It is such an instance that we are going to explore in our paper, and the subjects of this work are the youth of Veles, Macedonia, that have turned quite rich and famous by setting up a fake-news enterprise. They even managed to influence the 2016 United States presidential elections, and this is the reason why the case of these fake-news producers has been widely analyzed. We believe that emerging populist parties, like AUR in Romania have been using the same content strategies and consequently they made it to the Parliament. The novelty of our approach is that we explore the emerging content regimes made possible by the digital environment.

2. Some considerations on fake news

The subject of fake news in the new media has become prominent in recent years (Lazer et al. 2018). Their volume, speed, and prevalence have raised concerns as to the propriety of content, freedom of speech, pervasiveness, political consequences, as well as to the vulnerability of audiences on the mediation platforms (Hunt, Gentzkow 2017). We use the term fake news to define news that are not true but are perceived as such. These are part of the larger phenomenon of disinformation; that is deception through media (Ireton, Posetti, 2018).

The Freedom House Report on internet freedom pointed out that “online manipulation and disinformation tactics played an important role in elections in at least 18 countries over the past year” (2017). There are voices that point to the novelty of the context of post-truth (Higgins, 2016) and post-trust (Löfstedt, 2005), but there are yet others that argue that the phenomenon of disinformation is age old, and we are merely experiencing new forms of old practices (Posetti, Matthews 2018; Ireton, Posetti, 2018).

Nevertheless, the main novelty that the new media make possible is that consequential disinformation is no longer located mainly in the field of (authoritarian) politics, but has diversified and can be instrumentalised by regular people; like the case of the youth of Veles Macedonia has shown to the world (Subramanian, 2017). It might be as well the case that disinformation has always been much more pervasive than assumed, and it is only now becoming more visible in the context of the wide availability of new media; that has the capacity of leaving digital traces, unlike previous types of mediation.

3. The content optimization enterprises in Veles, Macedonia

The literature identifies two main drivers for fake news production. One is ideological, and the other is economic, profit based (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). In our own exploration, we set out to understand first-hand the driving forces behind the fake news enterprises from Veles, Macedonia.

We undertook a field research on the content enterprises from Veles; that is a small town, in Eastern Europe, in one of the republics of the former Yugoslavia. The subject became famous in a political context, the USA presidential elections from 2016; which were influenced by the fake news from Veles Macedonia. After the initial outburst of the subject of fake news from Veles carried out by journalists in 2016 and 2017, we undertook our own exploration in 2019 and 2020, in the context of the 2020 USA presidential elections.

The journalistic article that broke the news on this subject with first-hand reporting was that of Samanth Subramanian, from *Wired*, in 2017. Basically, this account was telling the story of a group of teenagers from Veles Macedonia that was operating more than a hundred sites with fake news.

The fact that triggered the outrage on the subject was the fact that the pro Trump fake news from Veles influenced the US elections from 2016. It was proven that in the eve of the elections the citizens from the United States had more exposure to fake news than to verified mainstream media news; and two of the top ten pro-Trump stories were coming from Veles, Macedonia (Silverman & Alexander in 2016). At the time when we undertook our research, our subjects were no longer teenagers, but young adults; yet doing the same thing, fake news; well, in their own words, internet marketing.

At the moment, there is a kind of moral panic emerging about the spread of fake news from the basements of Eastern Europe by 'malicious individuals to create and spread fake news in the absence of a worry' (Xinyi Zhou, Reza Zafarani & Kai Shu, Huan Liu, 2019). We argue instead that producing public interest content is not really lucrative, but producing fake news is.

This is actually one of the most worrying and consequential observations of this research. In this paper we only discuss one of the most prominent cases of fake news, but it is by no means a unique or isolated situation (Butcher, 2019). The recent success of the populist AUR Party in Romania; that had a minimum of financing but a maximum of Internet content making bears witness to a larger phenomenon.

4. The ethnographic approach to the content factories from Veles, Macedonia

We add to the rich journalistic descriptive material already available on the subject our own fieldwork. Moreover, we employ theoretical and methodological means of analysis that provide with grounded explanations. The theoretical perspectives we reside in are the sociological imagination, the critical political economy of communication, enriched by an anthropological sensitivity.

We explore the field of content optimization enterprises from Veles Macedonia using first-hand knowledge provided by the producers themselves. Moreover, direct observation performed in Macedonia adds to the qualitative understanding of this sphere of practice in its context. Free discussions with the people in Veles and nearby towns provided the understanding of the amplitude of the emulation that this activity created in the area. We built a corpus of semi-structured interviews from recurrent encounters with five fake news producers. These were corroborated with an unstructured interview with the internet marketing teacher behind the whole enterprise, Mirko Ceselkoski. While the young fake news producers asked for anonymity, their mentor agreed to have his identity disclosed. The interval of the fieldwork was between 2019 and 2020. The research is based on qualitative interviews, and observation, but not performed by a western journalist or researcher, but by a young Macedonian researcher, from a nearby town a Romanian researcher. We believe that this perspective brings the opportunity for ‘anthropology at home’ dimension (Mughal, 2015), of the practices and narratives of the content enterprises.

We applied on our corpus the method of critical discourse analysis as critical social analysis in the understanding proposed by Norman Fairclough (2012). We analyzed the interviews with fake news producers and their mentor against the larger context of the political economy of content production from Veles; and this makes this research qualitative, and grounded. We did not enforce our own categories of understanding onto the subjects but tried to grasp the meaning that the subjects gave to their enterprise. At times, letting people speak, listening, making sense of what they are saying; and not being orientalising, patronizing or condescending are the most difficult parts of the research enterprise.

The general themes of the interview guide referred to the activity itself, the reasons, and its perspectives. This is how we realised that these young people define their activity as internet marketing content optimisation. The frame of ‘fake news’ was discursively glued on them by the western journalists that have been approaching the subject. To be honest, these content optimisers from Veles do not really care whether the content is true or not, as long as it brings large traffic and nice advertising money; and this is a very consequential finding.

At the end of the day, we came to situate this internet marketing enterprise in a binary opposition with public service journalism, theoretically inspired by the structuralist tradition of deriving meaning from relational oppositions (Lévy-Strauss, 1958).

The binary opposition which became the matrix of understanding emerged in the very process of interpretation. The road to meaning was an inductive one, in our case. We realized that our little team was firmly conceptually situated in the realm of journalistic content as public service and came across a discourse on internet marketing as content optimization.

This contradiction was further illuminated by the liminal position of the Macedonian researcher from the team, who received an invitation to join the fake news team in the context of the 2020 presidential elections in the United States; but refused. The reasons for not jumping in the other boat further clarified our own normative standing, as well as the economic, cultural and social empowerment that this proposition could potentially bring to Sara.

The subject of the fake news phenomenon from Veles, Macedonia has become prominent in the context of the American presidential elections of 2016. Nevertheless, we have attempted to ethnographically understand both the political economy of the process, as well as the local narratives about content production. This approach allowed us to get a glimpse into the symbolic space of these young people, to give a voice to the subjects themselves, and avoid both the ethnocentric and the moralizing fallacies. The new phenomenon that we unveil is the blurring of the line between marketing and journalism as an emerging regime of new media content. The deep-seated problem that we identified was the instrumentalisation of content for lucrative ends, and this is our original contribution to this topic.

5. The narrative of internet marketing versus fake news

The results of the critical discourse analysis point to the fact that this enterprise is defined by the content producers as an internet marketing project. The underlying principles are mainly economic - traffic maximization and monetization. The aim of the content producers from Veles has always been optimizing the content for traffic ends, irrespective of truth. They just turned from commercial to political content, and then back to commercial content. The content they produce is not only political, but as well situated in many other lucrative areas: sports, cosmetics, transport etc. The principle is the same, content and traffic optimization by means of audience profiling, and the same can be said of the AUR strategy in Romania.

The people involved in content optimization from Veles Macedonia define what they do as internet marketing. This narrative is recurrent and spontaneously appears in the way the interviewees address the subject of their activity. We did not ask about internet marketing because in our mind the undertaking from Veles was poor journalism. The subjects of our research were puzzled about the idea of journalism:

**‘I have never worked in a journalism project and honestly speaking I have no idea what journalism is and how it functions’
(S1, 23 years old).**

‘I did not work, and I did not study journalism; I have no idea about the ways journalists choose the subjects they write about and how they write them’
(S2, 23 years old).

The fourth interviewer put it in very direct terms:

‘I will simply tell you that I never worked in this field, but I became a fake-journalist with a lot of money’
(S4, 23 years old).

The training that these young people received was on internet marketing, and their trainer was Mirko Ceselkoski, one of our interviewees. They paid for internet marketing classes, and it was rewarding. Consequently, the narratives of the interviewees are situated in the realms of marketing and advertising as means of making money:

‘Believe me, Facebook is the biggest social network for good marketing, my articles came to have a lot of traffic’
(S1, 23 years old);

‘I see fake news in contemporary society as a process whereby each person, not matter whether he has something to do with journalism or not, can make a lot of money and hit a big ‘success’ on the advertising scene.’
(S2, 23 years old)

The trainer himself defines his whole activity and symbolic capital in the same terms:

‘We only do marketing because, from my point of view, it is the most important thing in today’s world. These techniques not only help to develop fake news, but all types of marketing. This course is available as well in English and we have my students from abroad, aged 17 to 50 (...) It is never too late to learn something new in life’
(Mirko Ceselkoski).

The contents for the sites were determined by profiling the audience, and by delivering the content that the consumers wished to be exposed to. It was never important for the fake news producers that the contents be true or verified, but that they create large traffic and click bait. The larger the traffic, the more money the young subjects would receive in their accounts straight from Google. According to them, they would write about anything, as long as it pays off.

Therefore, the content enterprise from Veles Macedonia has not been intended to be journalism, but marketing. Marketing aims to fit the needs of the consumer with a product and/or service, and this is exactly what these young people are doing.

The discussion here is that what is acceptable for marketing is not acceptable for journalism, because journalism is a public service (Hallin & Mancini, 2007), while marketing is not.

The critical discourse analysis of our corpus revealed the deep seated market maximization principle in the practice of content management performed by the youth of Veles Macedonia and their instructor.

‘For me, the fake news phenomenon is the fake information that gets shaped after following the public opinion in the society.’
(S5, 24 years old).

Content is tailored to consumer profile, needs and expectations. The mentor of the Veles project explains the genealogy of the enterprise:

‘I created an online course whereby anybody has the opportunity to learn how to do good marketing. The course has video materials of over one hundred hours, and we all the time add new material. We have as well face to face courses.’
(Mirko Ceselkoski)

The marketing approach starts with a classical testing of the prospective markets:

‘We tested various subjects like content about sports, cosmetics, history, in order for the Americans to come towards our sites. At the end of the day we noticed that political subjects were extremely popular. At the same time, we tested Hillary and Trump subjects, and so we noticed that Trump’s public was much more active than that of Hilary; they wanted to support him, to hear good news about him’
(Mirko Ceselkoski).

Thus, if American supporters wanted to hear good news about Donald Trump, they would receive just that; only that it did not matter whether they were true or not.

We had to give a name to the phenomenon that we encountered; and we named it internet marketing, appropriating the definition given by the subjects themselves. Internet marketing has as departure point the consumer profiling just like classical marketing but content itself is fitted to the needs identified. In classical marketing, there is already a product or service, and marketing fits it to the prospective consumers (Koetler, 1967).

In internet marketing, the content itself gets shaped after the identification of the market, in a continuous tailoring of content to consumer needs.

*Source: unsplash.com.
Photo by Markus Winkler.*

While other products and services preexist and are promoted in a free market, in this case content is produced in order to fit the consumer expectations, and irrespective of truthfulness.

‘Nobody proposes me anything, I write because this is what I decided to do, especially that the important thing is that sometimes it is not myself that writes, but it happened a few times only to copy fake news from other pages and to post them on my own’
(S5, 24 years old).

The act of producing content is not the most important aspect; as it happens already existing one is being reused. Actually, within the fake news enterprise from Veles, the click-bait title and the illustrations attached to it are the most important aspects, and not the body of the text itself.

‘It is not difficult at all for me; I only have to pay attention to the title and the timing of posting’
(S5, 24 years old).

The mentor of this internet marketing project described the content processing:

‘The youth from Veles started to transcribe already existing news and to publish them, and I see nothing wrong in this because journalists do it as well, it is a common practice. After they say that their work was going well, they worked some more, they started to change the titles, because I spent time with them four times only to teach them how to make the titles more ‘shocking’. In due time, they started to change the content as well, they started to choose very good images, because the image is more important than the title and the content itself; before reading the title, the people watch the image’
(Mirko Ceselkoski).

Source: *freepik.com*.
Photo by *freepik*.

6. Symbolic capital and the fake news practice

The conclusion of the field research was that the fake news enterprise from Veles is an illustration of symbolic empowerment of the otherwise powerless. The entrepreneurial mantra that came along with the neoliberal ideology in Eastern Europe after the demise of socialism has been preaching individual initiative and the drive to be prosperous and make money. The youth of Veles Macedonia have been doing just that in their emerging market society, with the means that they have been having at hand.

‘One day I was chatting with my friends at the table and the main topic was how to make money and salaries that are much bigger than the salaries that we have in Macedonia, and we decided together to get involved in fake news’

(S2, 23 years old)

In classical sociological terms, these young people have stepped in the grey zone of deviance, by using opportunistic means for legitimate ends (Merton, 1968). The worst thing that could and did happen to the fake news producers was to lose their Facebook account:

‘There is always a risk when you invest; the biggest risk for me was that I lost my Facebook profile that I invested so much in (...) At the moment I am no longer allowed to have a Facebook profile’

(S1, 23 years old).

The opportunity to make easy money further enhanced all capital fronts: cultural, economic, and social (Bourdieu, 1986). This activity has been steadily augmenting in net terms the individual symbolic capital of the ones involved. They became digitally knowledgeable, rich, and popular. If we are to apply the theoretical understanding proposed by Pierre Bourdieu, the phenomenon of conversion allows for one type of capital to be used to acquire another: for example knowledge brings money, and money brings enhanced social networks in the community. This theoretical model has explanatory power, and was validated in the course of our research.

We came to realize that the three types of capital: cultural, economic and social have been enhancing each other all the way in this context, and solidify, rather than melt the vicious circle of fake news production. This practice started with cultural capital, the internet marketing knowledge; that enhanced the economic capital by means of advertising revenue from Google; that further brought a growing popularity and fame of the fake news producers, locally but as well internationally. Moreover, the social capital came in the form of a tightly knit group of fake news producers and admiring followers.

The process started with instruction in the field of internet marketing, provided by Mirko Ceselkoski. This represented the cultural capital that allowed the people involved to capitalize on this knowledge on the internet. The internet marketing knowledge further brought money from Google, and with the money came the fame and emulation.

The economic incentives provided by Google AdSense were enough to make any young person with no clear occupation or professional perspective engage in fake news, an easy to make money scheme. “On social media, the fixed costs of entering the market and producing content are vanishingly small. This increases the relative profitability of the small-scale, short-term strategies often adopted by fake news producers, and reduces the relative importance of building a long-term reputation for quality” (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017: 11). These young people are definitely digital literates, for they know how to navigate and incorporate what is technologically needed to optimize the contents that they circulate. “Rather than being social nuisances, the teenagers of Veles’ ability to manipulate the technical affordances of digital platforms and the affective reasoning of social media users, make them models par excellence for what it means to be digitally literate in an era of platform politics” (Pangrazio, 2018: 3). At the same time, their digital literacy alone does not make them proper citizens of the world. The larger question that is to be asked in this context is: Is digital literacy in itself conducive to a proper, thriving and all inclusive public sphere? The lesson from the Veles youth case is: NOT.

In terms of economic capital, the narratives of the young fake news producers are telling:

‘When it comes to benefits, the best outcome of publishing fake news was that salary; that was ten times bigger than a regular salary in Macedonia’
(S1, 23 years old);

‘Of course it is not correct to dis-inform because it can have negative effects on the public; but I am not very worried about it because it was the most profitable thing that I have ever done in my life’; ‘As I told you before, I no longer write fake news, but the friends that I worked with still do it and there is no reason to stop because it is about a lot of money’
(S1, 23 years old);

‘Fake news is a kind of business because with little work anybody can make a lot of money. There are too many people that think that this is illegal work, but from my point of view I have nothing against it’
(S1, 23 years old);

‘Fake news is a kind of profession for the money; that is very common among the youth lately because it brings easy money’
(S1, 23 years old);

‘Nobody can tell me to do things that I do not want, honestly it was my decision and I think it is a very good and quality idea, if you are considering the money!’
(S2, 23 years old);

‘I made 70000 EUROS, and this is not a small benefit, but a very good one’

(S4, 23 years old).

In terms of social capital, both the direct observation performed by the Macedonian researcher of the group, as well as the accounts of the fake news producers themselves, point to important levels of networking, fame, national and international popularity, as well as emulation at the local level:

‘Fake news became very popular in my town and together with my friends we decided to make a kind of business’

(S1, 23 years old);

‘Fake news for me is a kind of activity anybody can join in order to make a career or to become known in the world’

(S2, 23 years old);

‘The decision to do it was my own, but as I said it was very popular in my town.’

(S1, 23 years old)

The fake news producers are a group of people that know each other, and enforce each other:

‘We had a perfect plan; together with my friends we started to apply it not knowing exactly where it would take us to’

(S4, 23 years old).

There seems to be no sensible reason for the youth of Veles Macedonia to do anything else but fake news. If we are to consider the situation in a rational choice paradigm, it is only rational to aim to be rich, popular and well connected. The public service alternative to the individual empowerment and enhanced symbolic capital that fake news production brings would be journalistic hard labor with no distinctive positive prospects. In this situation, the commodity value of fake news is clearly higher than the public service value of quality journalistic content. We face the same dilemma in our everyday work as journalism academics. We train the students for the hard labor of quality journalism, but they find pleasure, and good revenues in the growing content marketing field.

While ‘technological utopian claims tend to focus on participation, deinstitutionalization, innovation, and entrepreneurialism, and assume that digital media are inherently emancipatory’ (Pickard, 2017: 49-50), it is equally possible that the deregulated, market-driven structuration of the Internet turns out to have its unexpected consequences in the shape of production and circulation of fake news.

Source: freepik.com.
Photo by Racool_studio.

7. Conclusion

The fake news production practices in the global communication ecosystem were the departure point of this research. It took a striking situation like that of Veles Macedonia to illuminate the gravity of problems and consequences that an overgrown internet marketing content enterprise can present to global citizenship. The alternative that is institutionalizing in the context of platform new media appears to be even less virtuous than first anticipated. What we actually witness is a new content environment where fake news, rather than real news thrive. We believe that this is the fundamental issue to be addressed if we are to aim for a better information ecosystem and informed citizenship.

The internet marketing enterprise made the youth of Veles Macedonia rich, famous, and respected. By discussing the types of empowerment that the fake news production gave to the youth of Veles Macedonia, we shed light on the emerging institutionalization of the marketing content regime in the global informational ecology; that is not likely to stop, but to thrive. The recent case of the populist AUR Party success points to the fact that Internet optimization practices are used in myriad of ways, and in various places. We believe that the fundamental question that we ought to answer as adults and educators is how to contribute to a structure whereby creating quality content rather than fake news empowers the content producers in the current fragile global informational ecosystem.

Source: unsplash.com.
Photo by Campaign Creators.

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